

Job Satisfaction Of Aceh Education Board Based Transformational Leadership Model

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 09, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 01, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Transformational Leadership, Employee Empowerment, Job Satisfaction</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4570410</p>	<p><i>Human resource is an important resource for organization effectiveness. The purpose of this study is to explain the effect of transformational leadership and employee empowerment on job satisfaction. This research was conducted at the General Bureau and the Regional Secretariat of Aceh which had samples of 100 employees. The analysis technique used was multiple linear regression analysis. The results showed that transformational leadership had a positive effect on job satisfaction and employee empowerment had a positive effect on job satisfaction. Suggestions that can be given in this study are that the agency should create a positive working relationship between leaders and employees and among fellow employees so that transformational leadership can be realized and job satisfaction can be improved, the leader should make the situation in the organization feeling comfortable so that employees feel comfortable working and make employees feeling part of the organization's family. The sense of kinship created will make employees better at work and provide good results at work.</i></p>

Introduction

A leader is the person who is able to guide, use his authority and direct the group to carry out tasks in order to achieve goals. Meanwhile, a leadership is the effort of a leader to coordinate, motivate, and influence the group behavior to achieve a goal. A successful institution is determined by the quality of leadership that can achieve the goals of the institution. The determination of the ups and downs of the institution progress depends on the method applied by a leader in the institution (Asmani, 2012: 9-10). Leadership is related to art and the ability to influence a person or group of people to act. Whereas management is the art and science of instructing people to act (Danim and Suparno 2009).

Leadership model is behavior and strategy, as a result of a combination of philosophy, skills, traits, attitudes, which are often applied by a leader to influence the performance of the people. According to Rivai (2014: 42), leadership model is a set of characteristics used by leaders to influence the people so that organization goals are achieved or a leadership model is a pattern of behavior and strategy that is favoured and often applied by a leader. There are two types of leadership model according to Ratnaningsih (2009: 126), namely a transactional leadership model and a transformational leadership model. Transactional leadership model is a leadership model in which uses rewards or penalties to motivate and measure the work performance, while a transformational leadership model is a leadership model that motivate the people by sentences. The ideal leadership model is a leadership model that has an emphasis on clear vision and mission statements, effective use of communication, intellectual stimulation, and personal attention to the individual problems of its members. All of these things are found in the national leadership model. Transformational leadership model need to be applied in various institutions.

Nowadays, leadership is still an interesting discussion to study and research, but there are only a few who understand. The problems, that found in Aceh Education Authority, are the lack of communication and trust between leaders and the people who are working at the institution, the lack of understanding that each individual has different needs, desires, and expertise, and the lack of cooperation due to feelings that the leader has the right to give orders to his subordinates.

Nowack (2004, 311: 313) examined the effect of leadership effectiveness on employee psychological health, including job satisfaction, motivation, stress, retention and employee performance. The results concluded that, employees think leaders who have bad leadership cause employees to tend to leave the

organization, low work motivation, unhealthy work circumference, higher stress. The results of this study support the hypothesis that leadership provides a significant influence on creating work motivation, including job satisfaction, stress and work atmosphere. In addition, leadership can create inspiration to have a sense of admiration, pride, and loyalty to employees so that creating motivation to perform tasks more than expected.

Based on the background explanation above, the authors formulated the research question as follows: How is the application of transformational leadership model within the Aceh Education Authority? The purpose of this study was to determine the application of transformational leadership model in the management of Aceh Education Authority. From the goals that have been formulated, the results of this study are expected to be able to contribute to the institution and can benefit for the wider community.

The results of this study are expected to provide examples of transformational leadership model to be applied in the implementation of management within Aceh Education Authority in order to improve the quality of existing human resources, provide input to the head of the Aceh Education Authority, Aceh.

Literature Review And Framework

2.1 Leader Member Exchange (LMX) Theory

Defined as an interpersonal exchange relationship between subordinates and their leaders (Ping and Yue, 2010). LMX theory found differences in attitudes received by subordinates from their superiors to form separate groups called in-group and out-group (Wijayanto and Susanto, 2013).

2.2 Principles of Transformational Leadership

The principles that must be created by a transformational leader, namely (Erik Rees, 2001) simplification, motivation, facilities, mobility, being ready, and determination.

2.3 Classical Motivation Theory

Frederick Winslow Taylor's motivation theory is called by a classical motivation theory, because he views the motivation of the theory workers from the point of fulfilling only biological needs. Biological needs are met through salary or wages provided. Therefore the leader is able to provide ideas or inspiration that can motivate his subordinates. This transformational leader model will arouse the enthusiasm and optimism of its employees.

Organizations or companies must know what is the satisfaction and dissatisfaction of employees, because there are five components of job satisfaction constructed by Azeem (2010) namely, payments (Pay), jobs (Job), promotion opportunities (promotion opportunities), superiors (supervisors), colleagues work (Co-workers).

2.4 Transformational leadership

Related to this transformational leadership, Lethwoot et al. (1999), write in Danim. S, (2003), Transformational leadership is sent to be sensitive to organizations building, developing share vision, distributing leadership and building school culture necessary to current restructuring efforts in school. This quote outlines that transformational leadership leads HR led to the growth of sensitivity in coaching and organizational development, development of a shared vision, distribution of leadership authority and building the organizational culture of institutions that are required in the institution's restructuring scheme.

2.4.1 Transformational Leadership Model

Most recent theories of transformational leadership are greatly influenced by James McGregor Burns, Burns distinguishes between transformational leadership and transactional leadership. Transformational leadership calls for the moral values of followers in an effort to increase their awareness to reform institutions, while transactional leadership motivates followers by calling for their personal interests.

2.4.2 Job Satisfaction

A person can work because there is a motivation to meet various needs, A.H. Maslow believes that the needs of a person who wants a tiered, meaning that if the first needs are met, then the second level needs will be the priority. Furthermore, if the second need has been met, then the third level needs to emerge and so on until the fifth level of need. Hence, A.H.'s motivational theory Maslow is called "A Theory of Human Motivation". This theory follows the plural theory that is someone behaves / works, because of the motivation to meet various needs / levels.

1.4.3 Framework

- a. Leadership model for job satisfaction.
- b. Transformation leadership towards job satisfaction.

- c. Employee / staff job satisfaction.

Research Methods

3.1 Research Design

The research approach used in this study was a qualitative approach. In terms of the aspects studied, this research is a case study (Case Study). Case study is a form of in-depth research on an aspect of the social environment including humans in it. In qualitative research and a case study approach according to Moleong, (2010) there are several stages carried out in data collection, the techniques used in this study were the pre-field stage, the field work stage, the data analysis stage, the evaluation, and the reporting stage.

3.2. Object of research

The object of the Transformational leadership model research based on job satisfaction are: the leader / agency leader and head of Aceh Education Authority, another reason for the research being conducted is the consideration that the transformational leadership model has not been fully implemented based on employee job satisfaction with behavioral values responsibility and motivation that occur within the Aceh Provincial Education Office organization. Therefore, this research methodology was descriptive qualitative research, by focusing on the problems and phenomena that exist when the research is carried out that is actual, then describes the facts about the problem under investigation, and interpreted rationally and accurately. Nawawi, (1990). The aims of this qualitative research method include understanding, interpreting how respondents in their environment shape the world around them, namely, description of a phenomenon, and the meaning of phenomenon interpretation, and theories based on that interpretation.

When viewed from the horizon team, this study is a cross section, meaning that information from the population is collected directly on the scene empirically, that aim to find out opinions and populations of the object being examined. (Umar, 2003: 203).

The respondents in this study are as follows:

No	Agency	Total	Information
1.	Leader	1	
2.	Secretary	1	
3.	Agency of Economic Development Planning and employment	1	
4.	Agency of construction of facilities planning and infrastructure	1	
5	Agency of planning of Aceh development and human resources	1	
6.	Agency of Program and development funding	1	
7.	Research and Development	1	
8	Agency of Development control and evaluation	1	6. People

3.2 Data Sources

Source of data used in this study consisted of primary and secondary data, primary data is data in the form of verbal or words spoken verbally, gestures or behavior carried out by subjects that can be trusted, namely research subjects or information regarding with the problems and objectives studied and data obtained from respondents directly through interviews, (Arikunto, 2010). Furthermore, secondary data that support this research, were obtained from the results of conservation and documentation related to job satisfaction based on transformational leadership models, (Arikunto, 2010).

3.3 Data Collection

Wiratna Sujarweni, (2014), said that the correct data collection method will produce data that has high credibility, therefore the data collection stage must not be wrong and must be done carefully according to procedures and characteristics of qualitative research, if it is wrong in the collection method, the data will be fatal. The data would has no credibility, so the results of the research cannot be justified, the data

collection techniques in this study were needed including interviews to the leaders and employees, observation, documentation, and study of the literature.

3.4 Data Analysis

Qualitative data analysis is an effort made by working with data, organizing data, sorting into something that can be managed, synthesizing it, searching and finding patterns, discovering what is important and what is learned, and deciding what can be told to others, the data analysis process is carried out simultaneously and continuously with the data collection process. Moleong (2010)

3.5 Research Instrument

The main research instruments were structured interviews, observation, and documentation, to test the quality of the data, the researchers have to focus on the theory applied

3.6 Research Stages:

1. Initial data collection stage
2. Planning stages
3. Research implementation stage

3.7 Location

The study was planned to be carried out within Aceh Education Authority. Street Tgk. Daud Beureuh Kuta Alam Banda Aceh City.

Result

4.1 Result

Aceh Education Authority is an institution under Aceh Government that focus on education sector, both formal and non-formal education.

Human Resources of Aceh Education Authority.

4.1.1 Based on the Gender

Human Resource Condition Based on the Gender

No.	Gender	Total	Percentage
1.	Male	4.998	36.17
2.	Female	8.821	63.83
	Total	13.819	100.00%

Source : Data is processed, 2020

4.1.2 Based on the Education Level

The Condition of HR of Aceh Education Authority Data Based on the Education Level

No.	Education	Total	Percentage
1	SD	16	0.12
2	SLTP	45	0.33
3	SLTA	937	6.78
4	D-I	12	0.09
5	D-II	106	0.77
6	D-III	290	2.10
7	D-IV	75	0.54
8	S-1	11.401	82.50
9	S-2	919	6.65
10	S-3	8	0.06
11	Profession	10	0.07
	Total	13.819	100.00%

Source : Data is processed, 2018

4.1.3 Based on the Rank and Class Category

The State Civilian Personal Condition of Aceh Employment Agency Based on Class Category

No	Rank and Class Category	Total	Percentage
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1	Young Proficient (I/a)	3	0.02
2	Young Proficient Tk. I (II/b)	6	0.04
3	Proficient (I/c)	29	0.21
4	Proficient Tk. I (II/d)	23	0.17
5	Young Regulator (II/a)	207	1.50
6	Young Regulator Tk. I (II/b)	352	2.55
7	Regulator, (II/c)	297	2.15
8	Regulator Tk I, (II/d)	197	1.43
9	Young Administrator, (III/a)	1.395	10.09
10	Young AdministratorTk. I, (III/b)	1.211	8.76
11	Administrator, (III/c)	2.391	17.30
12	Administrator Tk. I, (III/d)	2.627	19.01
13	Supervisor, (IV/a)	2.568	18.58
14	Supervisor Tk. I, (IV/b)	2.488	18.00
16	Young Supervisor, (IV/c)	25	0.18
17	Primary Supervisor, (IV/d)	-	-
Total		13.819	100%

Source : Data is processed, 2018

Discussion

4.2 The Effect of Job Satisfaction toward the performance

Robbins, (2012) explains that if an employee has high job satisfaction, he will have a positive feeling towards the job itself and vice versa. If someone does not have job satisfaction, he will have a negative feeling about the work. In other words, employees who have a sense of job satisfaction will tend to provide better jobs. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Rosita and Yuniati, (2016), Novita, et al, (2016).

4.3 The Effect of Transformational Leadership toward the Performance

Leadership model must be able to inspire the people by giving priority to the organizational development rather than personal interests and give more attention to the people and they are able to change employee perceptions to work better in helping companies to achieve company goals (Muchran and Muchran, 2017). The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Tucunan, et al., (2014), Cahyono, et al., (2014), Amri, et al. (2016), which concluded the results of his research that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on improving employee performance. If transformational leadership is applied optimally, it will be able to improve employee performance.

4.4 The effect of job satisfaction and transformational leadership on performance simultaneously

Robbins and Judge, (2009) explain that leadership has four characteristics, namely "idealized influence (attributed or behavioral), inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration" ", the concept of leadership emphasizes that subordinates will have a sense of trust, admiration, pride, loyal and respecting superiors then subordinates will be motivated to carry out work with the results that have been targeted by the company and finally employees will feel satisfaction (Indrawati, 2013). Transformational leaders can also help employees to be creative and innovative that can bring the company to grow competitively and adapt to the changing of external environment, so that it can be concluded that transformational leadership behavior can increase employee satisfaction and performance (Indrawati, 2013).

Conclusion

Job satisfaction and transformational leadership partially and simultaneously had a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This showed that the company managers must be able to provide employee satisfaction by optimizing the various facilities that exist in the company, as well as its transformational leadership must be applied in the company so that employee performance can improve, while the most dominant in influencing performance was transformational leadership. So that transformational leadership must be able to be applied by managers in the company, so that along with and in

line with employees will get satisfaction and have an impact on increased performance, so that the role of job satisfaction and transformational leadership is very important to apply. In further research, in order to develop variables in job satisfaction research and transformational leadership variables, future studies indicators of job satisfaction and transformational leadership can be used as research variables, so that theories about job satisfaction and transformational leadership can develop and be useful for the development of science

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